

Learning Contact-Rich Tasks for the Industry 5.0

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I. INTRODUCTION

Over recent years, industrial automation has witnessed growing interest in integrating robotic systems for repetitive tasks to increase productivity, enabling the human to face more cognitively demanding activities. However, offloading tasks to robots is not always straightforward, especially when the task requires human-like skills, such as polishing, grinding, or cleaning. In these cases, the robot needs to physically interact with the workpiece, and the surface geometry, which is usually complex, plays a crucial role in the task execution. This problem is even more challenging in the context of flexible manufacturing, where the assembly lines is often reconfigured to produce new products, and relying on offline trajectory generation is not feasible.

In this scenario, Learning from Demonstration (LfD) [1] paved the way for transferring human expertise and knowledge to robotic systems by observing human behaviour. After the acquisition of robot trajectories by means of visual observation or physical guidance, also known as kinesthetic teaching, a simple tool that can be use to encode the end-effector motion is provided by Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) [2]. This method describes the trajectory as a stable non-linear dynamical system that, starting from a single demonstration, is capable to generalise motion from different starting configurations, and reaching different goal positions, without modifying the shape of the path. Even tough the original formulation was able to encode only vectorial quantities, such as the end-effector position, DMPs have been extended to work on Riemannian manifolds [3], i.e., on other mathematical domains, such as hyperspheres that can represent the orientation of the end-effector.

Literature on LfD investigated the problem of learning and executing complex motions on surfaces, to accomplish tasks such as polishing, grinding, and cleaning. Common strategies include hybrid force-position control of the end-effector to achieve a stable contact of the surface, and use surface normal estimation to ensure the end-effector stays in a desirable pose when moving on a flat surface. Other approaches, instead, rely on the control of the whole end-effector pose control, and integrate impedance strategies to handle contacts.

With this work, we provide an insight on our recent works

Co-funded by the European Union projects INVERSE (grant agreement no. 101136067) and MAGICIAN (grant agreement no. 101120731)

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that tackles the problem of executing contact-rich tasks on surfaces.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Variable Impedance Control

Variable impedance control is a widely known strategy that manages the physical interaction of a robot with the environment. Impedance controllers in fact tries to render the wrench \mathbf{h} at the end-effector as a spring-damper system, like $\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{M}\ddot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} + \mathbf{D}\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} + \mathbf{K}\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$. Here, $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ is the tracking error of the robot over a reference in the Cartesian space, and $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K}$ are the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices, respectively.

By tuning these matrices, we can control the entity of the robot interaction with the environment. In [4], we regulate the stiffness \mathbf{K} during the execution to achieve an optimal trade-off between having a desired stiffness \mathbf{K}^{des} , that enables the robot to correctly track the reference position, and a desired wrench \mathbf{h}^{des} applied by the end-effector, which is used to accomplish the contact task.

Since variable impedance control schemes can violate the passivity of the system by providing the environment more energy than the one the robot received, we introduced an energy-tank on the power-port $\mathbf{h}^T \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}}$. The stiffness of the impedance model is finally obtained by solving a QP problem that integrates constraints on the energy and the power flow of the tank, avoiding condition in which the robot exerts high forces in an unsafe manner.

B. DMPs on manifolds

To encode motion skills from demonstration, we can use the geometry-aware formulation of DMPs proposed in [3]; by considering the motion as evolving on a manifold M , we can encode both the position in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 , as well as the orientation of the end-effector, either as unit quaternion $\mathbb{S}(3)$ or rotation matrix $SO(3)$. Dealing with periodic motions, we rely on rythmic DMPs, non-linear oscillators whose dynamic on a manifold defined as

$$\nabla_z z = \Omega (\alpha (\beta \text{Log}_{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{g}) - z) + \mathbf{f}(\phi)), \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}} = \Omega z, \quad (2)$$

$$\Omega \dot{\phi} = 1. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathbf{y} \in M$ is the position state, $z \in T_{\mathbf{y}}M$ the (scaled) velocity state, where $T_{\mathbf{y}}M$ is the tangent space at \mathbf{y} , $\mathbf{g} \in M$ the centre of the motion, $\mathbf{f} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow T_{\mathbf{y}}M$ the forcing function which is learned from demonstration, $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^+$ a temporal scaling coefficient, and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ coefficients associated to the linear dynamics.

Fig. 1. Framework proposed in [4].

Fig. 2. Snapshots taken from an experiment in which framework in Fig. 1 is used to learn polishing operation involving also the re-orientation of the end-effector. Full video available at <https://youtu.be/2fCSnqNbqz0>.

C. Incremental Learning Framework

Based on variable impedance control and DMPs, in [4] we propose a framework, Fig. 1, to incrementally learn contact-rich motions. Here, we proposed a novel formulation of autonomy level, a coefficient $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ which enables the smooth interleaving of learning ($\gamma = 0$) and autonomous ($\gamma = 1$) execution phases. The dynamic encompasses mainly two contributions: one associated to the tracking error, that when low pushes the autonomy level to 1, and one related to the energy-tank power flow that, when high, pushes the autonomy level to 0.

From a high-level perspective, our framework is an autonomous system since it does not involve any external control input at runtime. Transition from learning to autonomous execution, and vice-versa, are triggered by the system itself, in particular based on the physical interaction that the robot establishes with the environment and the human.

The autonomy coefficient is used to properly tune the learning coefficient ζ , a parameter that regulates the learning rate of both the forcing function f of the DMP (1), and the adaptive frequency oscillator module that estimates online the period of the demonstrated motion.

III. EXPERIMENTS

To validate the proposed incremental learning framework, we carried out several experiments using a Universal Robots UR5e robot to perform wiping operations on arbitrary surfaces. An example of such experiment is depicted in Fig. 2.

The system initially starts still in learning mode, thus the desired stiffness \mathbf{K}^{des} of the impedance model is set to a low value, effectively putting the robot in gravity compensation mode, allowing the teaching of a new task. As the human shows a task, the system starts to learn the forcing function f ; this, in turn, will reduce the tracking error, and consequently the autonomy level γ will increase. As the system is learning, the desired stiffness \mathbf{K}^{des} is gradually increased; this increase in stiffness has a dual effect: it enables the robot to better track its own generated reference, as well

Fig. 3. Preliminary results of a DMP-based approach to perform integration on discrete surfaces.

as it provides a valuable feedback to the human operator, that can feel the robot is getting autonomous. To revert the execution mode from autonomous to learning, the human operator can physically interact with the robot. Such action will instantaneously inject lots of energy in the energy-tank, triggering the reduction of the autonomy level γ .

The proposed framework can be used by any person, even without any prior knowledge of robotics, to online teach the robot new tasks. By learning the motion in the whole operational space of the robot, the system can also learn tasks that involve re-orientation of the end-effector, improving the versatility of the system.

IV. ONGOING WORKS

Even though the proposed framework can efficiently learn motion pattern in the Cartesian space and safely execute contact-rich wiping tasks, it does not exploit the intrinsic geometry of the surface, making it impossible to generalise learned policies to different surfaces. To address this issue, we are currently working on the definition of differential operators that will enable the use of DMPs on discrete manifolds, in particular on triangular meshes.

A preliminary result is shown in Fig. 3, where a rhythmic DMP, trained on a flat surface, is integrated on the front fender of a car. By learning and executing motion directly within the mesh domain, we guarantee that the planned motion is feasible and always in contact with the surface. Moreover, with this approach we plan to generalise learned policies to arbitrary surfaces, by providing a parameterisation of the forcing term f in (1) which is agnostic to the specific mesh used.

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